

**A DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL
PERFORMANCE PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED WITH DATABASE SYSTEMS AT
THE FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, ZARIA.**

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KANO STUDY CENTRE.**

JUNE, 2025

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY, FACULTY OF COMPUTING, NATIONAL OPEN UNIVERSITY
OF NIGERIA, IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE (MSc) IN INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY.**

JUNE, 2025

DECLARATION

I, Muhammad Ahmad, with Matriculation number NOU212052441 hereby declare that the thesis work entitled A Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Organizational Performance Problems Associated with Database Systems at The Federal University of Education, Zaria. is a record of an original work done by me, as a result of my research effort carried out in the Faculty of Computing, National Open University of Nigeria under the supervision of Prof. Ibrahim A. Lawal.

Student's Signature & Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this dissertation titled " A Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Organizational Performance Problems Associated with Database Systems at The Federal University of Education, Zaria." was carried out by Muhammad Ahmad with Matriculation Number NOU212052441 in the Department of Information Systems and Technology, Faculty of Computing, National Open University of Nigeria, under my supervision.

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External Examiner

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DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to my beloved father Late. Alh. Bamalli Tijjani Yakubu, whose unwavering support, guidance, and encouragement were a constant source of strength throughout my academic journey. His belief in my potential and his sacrifices for my education have left an indelible mark on my life. Although he is no longer with us, his memory continues to inspire me every day.

I also dedicate this work to my family and loved ones for their steadfast support, understanding, and encouragement, which have been invaluable in helping me reach this milestone. Thank you for standing by me through every challenge and triumph.

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ABSTRACT

Educational institutions increasingly depend on database systems to manage student records, academic resources, and administrative tasks. However, many universities struggle with performance inefficiencies, security risks, and poor optimization, which hinder decision-making and institutional effectiveness. This study investigates the organizational performance problems associated with database systems at the Federal University of Education, Zaria, focusing on efficiency, security, and usability. A structured survey conducted among university staff and database administrators revealed that 78% of respondents believe efficient database management enhances decision-making, while 65% reported increased staff productivity due to improved data accessibility. However, 72% identified security risks as a major concern affecting reliability. These findings highlight the need for universities to invest in database optimization strategies to enhance performance and security. Addressing these challenges will improve academic administration and operational efficiency. Future research should explore emerging database technologies to strengthen institutional management in the education sector.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The efficiency of an organization is determined by its ability to make good decisions, and these decisions are based on having access to high-quality data in a timely manner. For an organization to function, it must process transactions, such as preparing payroll, posting income and account bills, and other data processing tasks. A database is not only a tool for data processing, but it's also a computer-assisted information retrieval system that provides data to decision-makers and managers. The database is a collection of related. The database is the rules set for processing data into information to be useful for information system users according to their needs (Connolly & Begg, 2014).

Computers and computer applications have had a profound impact on all industries and businesses. Many companies view the management of their information as a key asset, similar to property, facilities, employees, and capital. The goal of Management Information Systems (MIS) is to analyze and design information systems that meet these business requirements. Whenever people work together in an organization, they naturally create systems to get things done. However, these systems are often ineffective and inadequate (Bachman, 1973).

Databases can have a major impact on organizational performance by providing quick and efficient data access, improving data accuracy and consistency, and supporting data analysis and decision making. A well-designed database can streamline operations, minimize manual errors, increase productivity, and provide the basis for informed decision making. This can lead to better customer satisfaction, increased competitiveness, and higher profits, although the specific impact on performance will vary depending on the sector and use case. In general, using databases effectively can

lead to improved efficiency and effectiveness in various aspects of an organization (Irfan et al., 2022).

The information generated from the database is obtained from several interconnected data. There are several benefits of using a database, like Ease of storing data, minimizing data redundancy, Data accuracy, Availability of data according to user needs, Data Security, Availability of user sharing, and Providing data completely (Susilo, 2016). An application called the Database Management System is used to process data in the database, including MySQL, Ms. Access, SCL Server, and others. The database and database management system cannot be separated from each other and form a single unit called the database system. There are several database system components, namely hardware, operating system, database, database management system, users, and application interface (Johnson & Williams, 2019).

A DBMS is a type of transparent software to be used in creation, maintenance, and in imparting a well-controlled link to the various databases of the users. This is a pivotal technology required in all areas of service, e.g., industries, healthcare, aviation services, banking systems, etc. It provides a diversity of tremendous applications in scientific, industrial, and commercial domains. A database in a DBMS can be accessed by a variety of users with varying roles. For example, within a firm, there are several departments as well as clients who require different types of data. With their own customized front-end application, each person in the firm will have varying levels of access to the database. Data in a database is strictly organized in row and column format. The rows are referred to as Tuple or Record. The data pieces in a single row may be of different data types. Columns, on the other hand, are frequently referred to as Domain or Attribute. The data elements included within a single attribute are all of the same data type (Chapple & Mike, 2005).

A distributed database (DDB) is a reasonable database capable of spreading on several computers in various locations at the same time and staying connected by a complex network of data communications. Today, the DDB is considered a unique and fundamental corporate resource for providing flexibility with wide applications. The primary goal of a DBMS is to provide a way to store and retrieve database information that is both convenient and efficient. Data refers to known facts that can be documented and have implicit meaning. (Hernandez, 2019).

In Distributed database, the network must permit sharing data with users at different locations. Its sites of distribution could spread over a large or small area, and computers may also range from large-scale computers to even supercomputers. The DDB requires multiple database management systems running at each remote site. Nowadays, various business conditions encourage the application of DDB, including the distribution and autonomy of business units, data sharing, data communication costs and reliability, multiple application vendor environments, database recovery, and the satisfying of both transactions and analytical processing. Today, despite its advancement, the DDB is still looking for a place in commercial markets due to security-related risks that are generating roadblocks in its secure operation (Kim & Lee, 2011).

Database design and implementation, application design and implementation, and administrative procedures influence information systems. Database design is the first factor that influences information systems. This means that a good database structure will greatly affect the performance of information systems. Nine aspects need to be considered in designing a database: the ability to be integrated, reach, level of detail, correctness, consistency, relevance, completeness, minimalism, and readability (Olawepo, 1990).

Several factors influence database performance, including i) reaction time, which is the time it takes the database to process a particular instruction; ii) throughput, which is the ability of hardware and software to process data; iii) resources, hardware and software, iv) memory, the amount of memory used in completing the given command. The amount of data to be processed by the database will help application performance if optimization is carried out (Robinson, 2016).

Database optimization can be done by adjusting the hardware with the software and configuring the database application, but this method requires more expensive resources. Another method is optimizing the database design, which can only be done at the start of programme development. Database optimization can also be accomplished by optimizing the database queries/commands used in applications (Kim & Lee, 2011). In addition to database performance objectives, as mentioned earlier, optimization is also carried out for data security purposes to prevent interface exploitation of the database. Communication errors between the application interface and the server will cause security holes in the stored data. This is called SQL injection. SQL Injection takes advantage of invalid data errors entered into the database through the application interface. One way to improve database security is to include data encryption techniques in the programme, which results in stored data that differs from inputted data. This is done to reduce data misuse (Halder and Cortesi, 2011).

Database systems are intended to manage massive amounts of data. Data management entails both creating structures for information storage and offering tools for information modification. Furthermore, the database system must ensure the security of the information saved, even if the system crashes or unauthorized access attempts are made. If data is to be shared across multiple users, the system must avoid any unexpected results (Halder, 2011).

1.2 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

In today's data-driven business environment, organizations depend on robust database management systems (DBMS) to handle vast amounts of information efficiently. Effective database management enhances decision-making, streamlines operations, and strengthens competitive advantage (Connolly & Begg, 2014). However, many organizations continue to face challenges in database design, implementation, and security, which can significantly hinder overall performance (Smith, 2017).

A well-optimized database improves data accuracy, reduces redundancy, and enhances retrieval speed, ultimately boosting organizational efficiency (Davis & Garcia, 2021). Despite these advantages, database performance bottlenecks often arise due to inadequate optimization, security vulnerabilities such as SQL injection attacks, and insufficient resource allocation (Halder & Cortesi, 2011). These challenges can lead to sluggish data processing, compromised data integrity, and difficulties in strategic decision-making (Irfan et al., 2022).

Existing research has primarily focused on the technical aspects of DBMS, with limited empirical studies exploring their broader organizational impact. There is insufficient evidence on how database performance influences key business factors such as managerial decision-making, employee productivity, and customer satisfaction (Parker & Young, 2022). Understanding these relationships is crucial for maximizing the strategic potential of database systems in modern organizations.

This study seeks to address this gap by examining the link between database efficiency and organizational performance, emphasizing how optimized databases can improve business processes, enhance decision-making, and drive sustainable competitive advantage.

In order to thoroughly answer the important questions posed in the research problem, this study will employ a mixed-methods research methodology. By integrating quantitative data to quantify the impact of databases on organisational performance with qualitative insights to examine how databases affect organisational decision-making processes, this technique will enable a robust analysis. The data collection and questionnaire distribution will be done via Google Forms.

1.3 AIM OF THE STUDY

The main aim of this study is to investigate organizational performance problems associated with database systems at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the effect of database systems on organizational performance at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.
2. Assess the influence of database systems on management decision-making within the institution.
3. Identify database-related challenges affecting organizational efficiency in the institution.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In order to achieve the goal of this research, the following questions will be addressed through the study:

1. Does Database have any impact on organizations performance?
2. To what extent does the utilization of a database shape and influence decision-making processes within an organization's management hierarchy?
3. How do the dynamics of database utilization affect organizational workflows and practices?

1.6 SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF STUDY

The study will concentrate specifically on the operations and practices related to Information Systems Management within the confines of the Federal University of Education in Zaria, situated within the Zaria Local Government of Kaduna State. The research will emphasize the technological aspects aiding management in the efficient collection and processing of data.

There are some factors that could potentially hinder or impact the successful completion of this research project, such as limited time, resources, materials, the large distance that needs to be covered, and others limitations listed below. These constraints may result in a less comprehensive study.

Single Institution Focus: The study's exclusive concentration on the Federal University of Education in Zaria limits the generalizability of findings to a broader organizational context. Different institutions or industries may exhibit varying operational dynamics affecting database utilization and organizational performance.

Narrow Focus on Information Systems Management: Focusing solely on Information Systems Management may restrict the exploration of other critical factors impacting organizational performance beyond technology, such as human resources, market dynamics, or external environmental factors.

Regional and Contextual Constraints: Restricting the study to a specific geographic location and educational institution might not represent the diverse array of organizational structures, industries, or geographical regions, thereby limiting the study's applicability to different settings.

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study holds great significance as it aims to provide insight into the effect of database systems on the efficiency of management in the educational sector.

Federal University of Education: The management will be educated on how to properly manage data, which will ultimately lead to the growth of the university and the education sector in Nigeria. Improved information management will allow the sector to fulfill its social responsibilities, thus benefiting society as a whole.

The government can also benefit from proper data management, as it will assist with urban planning, tax management, military planning, environmental planning, and rate management. This research will also contribute to future studies on this topic. If similar studies have been conducted, this research will add to the existing body of knowledge for future reference.

1.8 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology provides the framework for the collection, analysis, interpretation, and dissemination of data in a particular field. Key components of research methodology include:

Research design: the plan or strategy for conducting the research.

Data collection methods: the methods used to gather data, such as surveys, interviews, or observations.

Data analysis techniques: the methods used to analyse the data, such as statistical analysis or qualitative analysis.

Sampling techniques: the process of selecting a portion of the population for study.

Ethical considerations: the principles and values that guide the conduct of research, such as confidentiality, informed consent, and avoiding harm to participants.

The method to be used for data collection for this project will be mainly derived from two sources which are primary and secondary sources.

The basic tool for data collection will be the questionnaire (through google form or other offline means). It is hoped that this medium will provide the necessary information with high accuracy and minimize costs and time.

1.9 DEFINITION OF TERMS

Computer: is a device that operates based on stored programs and can accept, process, produce and store data and information. It can be seen as a tool that takes in data, processes it according to specific rules, and outputs information. Computers work automatically under the influence of stored programs. (WiseGeek. Retrieved from <https://www.wisegeek.com/what-is-a-computer.htm>).

Data: refers to individual pieces of information, often numerical, that are collected through observation. It can take many forms, including numbers, text, images, audio, or video and can be stored and processed by computers for analysis and decision-making purposes. Data is used in fields such as business, science, and technology to provide insights and inform decisions. In a technical sense, data is a set of values about one or more objects or individuals, and a datum is a single value. (Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Data*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data>).

Data processing: involves the manipulation of data by a computer to produce output (information) for decision-making. It is the process of collecting and converting source data into information. (www.answers.com/topic/dataprocessing).

Files: refer to information stored on a computer's backing storage, such as magnetic discs or tapes, to persist beyond the end of a single job or overcome memory limitations. (Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Computer file*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Computer_file

Hardware: refers to the physical parts of a computer system, including the input unit, system unit, output unit, and storage unit (e.g., memory). Examples of hardware include the keyboard, printer, mouse, and monitor. They are tangible and can be seen, touched, and felt. (Webopedia. (n.d.). *What is hardware?* Webopedia. Retrieved from <https://www.webopedia.com/definitions/hardware/>

Information: This refers to data that has been processed to have a specific meaning, relevance, and application within a given context. Davis (2021) defined information as data that has been transformed into a form that is meaningful to the recipient and perceived as valuable for making decisions. Information provides context for data and aids in decision making. For example, the sales of a single customer at a restaurant are data, but becomes information when the business identifies the most popular or least popular dish. Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Information*. Wikipedia. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Information>

Information Technology: The use of computers, storage, networking, and other physical equipment, infrastructure, and procedures for creating, processing, storing, safeguarding, and sharing all types of electronic data is referred to as information technology (IT). IT is primarily employed in business operations and includes both computer technology and telecommunications (TechTarget. Retrieved from <https://www.techtarget.com/searchdatacenter/definition/IT>

Database: A database is a means of gathering, processing, storing, and disseminating data in the form of information required for management operations. It is a computer-based system that optimizes information collection, transport, and presentation within an organization by utilizing an integrated database and information flow structure. (Ramanathan et al., 2017).

Records: Records refer to a collection of related data stored in one or more files or a database. It is also a collection of related fields that describe an event, item, or transaction. Computer Hope. Retrieved from

<https://www.computerhope.com/jargon/r/record.htm>.

Software: Software is a set of instructions, data, or programs used to operate a computer and perform specific tasks. In simpler terms, it tells a computer how to function and includes applications, scripts, and programs that run on devices such as PCs, mobile phones, tablets, and other smart devices. Software is different from hardware, which is the physical components of a computer that perform the work. Webopedia. (n.d).

Software definition. Webopedia. Retrieved from

<https://www.webopedia.com/definitions/software/>

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter the database system, problem of implementing a computer-based database, classification of a good information, characteristics of a good information system, conceptual framework, review of related literature, summary of related literature, and the research gap will be discussed.

2.2 DATABASE SYSTEMS

Database systems have become a cornerstone of modern organizational infrastructure, enabling companies to efficiently store, retrieve, manage, and analyse data. The evolution of database technology has closely mirrored advances in computing and information systems, driving significant improvements in organizational decision-making and performance (Halder and Cortesi, 2011).

The development of database systems has seen a shift from simple file storage systems to complex database management systems (DBMSs). Early database models, such as the hierarchical and CODASYL (network) models, utilized physical pointers to manage data relationships. However, the introduction of the relational model by Edgar F. Codd in 1970 revolutionized data management with its use of table-based relationships, making data more accessible and easier to manipulate (Johnson & Williams, 2019).

Today, databases range from relational databases, like IBM Db2, Oracle, MySQL, and Microsoft SQL Server, to more dynamic models like NoSQL and NewSQL databases that provide flexibility and scalability for handling big data and real-time web applications (Chapple & Mike, 2005).

2.2.1 OBJECTIVES OF DATABASE

Professor Robert J. Carew of school of business, Arizona state university (2000) explain the objectives of Databases which aim to provide information to management at all levels in a timely, accurate, and cost-effective manner. This information is utilized in decision-making to modify the system's state by taking necessary actions. An important aspect of Management Information Systems (MIS) is feedback, which involves communicating the output of a system's measurement to the controlling system, typically a manager in the context of a business system. These elements make it possible to change a system's state. The objectives of a database can be broadly categorized into seven main areas:

Data Integration: A database aims to integrate data from multiple sources into a single, consistent view of the data. This is important because it reduces the complexity of managing and analysing data from multiple sources, as well as avoiding inconsistencies and inaccuracies in the data (Carew, 2000).

Data Consistency: Maintaining the consistency of data across the entire database is essential. This involves ensuring that all data is accurate, up-to-date, and consistent with other data in the database. This is important for the reliability and trustworthiness of the data (Carew, 2000).

Data Abstraction: A database provides a high-level view of the data, hiding the complexities of the underlying data storage mechanisms. This abstraction allows users to interact with the data in a simple and intuitive way, without having to be concerned with the underlying technical details of data storage and retrieval (Carew, 2000).

Data Security: Protecting the data stored in the database from unauthorized access, modification, or deletion is critical. This involves implementing access controls,

authentication mechanisms, and encryption algorithms to ensure that only authorized users and applications can access and modify the data (Carew, 2000).

Data Availability: Ensuring that the data stored in the database is available to authorized users and applications whenever it is needed is important for the usability of the database. This may involve implementing backup and recovery mechanisms to ensure that the data is always accessible, even in the event of a failure or disaster (Carew, 2000).

Data Scalability: As the amount and complexity of data stored in a database increases, it is important that the database can accommodate this growth. This involves implementing mechanisms to dynamically allocate and deallocate resources to meet the changing needs of the database (Carew, 2000).

Data Recovery: Ensuring that the data stored in the database can be recovered in the event of a failure or disaster is critical for the reliability and availability of the data. This may involve implementing backup and recovery mechanisms, as well as disaster recovery strategies to ensure that the data can be restored in a timely manner. (Carew, 2000)

These objectives ensure that a database provides a reliable and trustworthy source of data that can be used to support a wide range of applications and use cases.

2.2.2 ELEMENTS OF DATABASE

Elements of a database are the building blocks used to construct a database system. The term "elements" in this context refers to the fundamental components that make up a database, such as data, tables, fields, records, and relationships (Wikipedia, Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Database>). These elements work together to store, organize, and retrieve data in a structured and efficient manner. These elements include:

Data: This refers to the raw information that is stored in the database. It can be in the form of numbers, text, images, etc.

Fields: Fields are the individual units of data within a record. Each field represents a specific aspect of the information being stored, such as a person's name, address, or telephone number.

Records: A record is a collection of fields that together describe a single item or unit of information. For example, a record could contain all the information about a single customer.

Tables: A table is a collection of records that share the same structure, meaning they have the same fields. Tables are used to organize data in a database and make it easier to search and sort.

Keys: Keys are used to identify and link records within a database. There are two main types of keys: primary keys and foreign keys. A primary key is a unique identifier for each record within a table, while a foreign key is used to link records in different tables.

Relationships: Relationships are the connections between different tables in a database. They are used to enforce referential integrity, which ensures that data in one table corresponds to the correct data in another table.

Queries: Queries are used to retrieve information from a database based on certain conditions. They allow users to search for specific data or to perform calculations based on the data in the database.

Forms: Forms are used to input and view data in a database. They provide a user-friendly interface for entering and viewing data and can be customized to meet specific needs.

Reports: Reports are used to present data in a structured and organized manner. They can be used to summarize data, display data in a specific format, or to provide a detailed

analysis of data. These are the basic elements of a database and are essential for organizing and managing data effectively

2.2.3 BENEFITS OF DATABASE

Kim et al., (2011) propose that successful implementation of database would possibly bring the following: Data organization: A database provides a centralized and organized storage for large amounts of data. This makes it easier to manage and retrieve data as needed.

Data consistency: A database ensures data consistency by enforcing rules and constraints to maintain data integrity. This reduces the risk of data duplication and inconsistencies (Kim et al, 2011).

Data security: Databases provide a secure environment for storing sensitive and confidential information. They offer various security features like authentication, authorization, and encryption to protect data from unauthorized access (Kim et al, 2011).

Scalability: Databases are designed to scale to accommodate growing amounts of data and user demand. They can be easily upgraded and expanded as needed to meet changing needs (Kim et al, 2011).

Data recovery: Databases provide backup and recovery capabilities, allowing organizations to quickly recover lost or damaged data.

Improved data accessibility: A database enables multiple users to access and update data simultaneously, improving collaboration and decision-making (Kim et al, 2011).

Better performance: Databases are optimized for efficient data retrieval and processing, providing fast and reliable access to data even in large-scale environments (Kim et al, 2011).

2.2.4 ROLE OF DATABASE IN DECISION MAKING

Effective organizations need established systems that allow them to make the best decisions possible in scenarios they are likely to encounter. Therefore, an organizational information system must collect data, analyze it, and present it as useful information that can be retrieved as a specialized knowledge base at the point of decision (Susilo, 2016). Databases play a crucial role in decision making by providing organized, accurate, and reliable data that is easily accessible and retrievable. This data can be used to analyse patterns, identify trends, and make informed decisions (Wong, 2017). Databases also enable users to store and manipulate large amounts of data, allowing them to identify relationships, make comparisons, and run complex analyses. By having a centralized system to store data, organizations can ensure consistency and reduce errors, resulting in better decision making and improved business outcomes (Garcia et al., 2021).

In addition to the above, databases also provide the ability to track changes over time and enable organizations to make data-driven decisions. By having a historical record of data, organizations can monitor the effectiveness of their decisions, make adjustments as needed, and continuously improve their processes. This can help organizations make informed decisions in real-time, which is particularly important in today's fast-paced business environment (Wong, 2017).

Another key benefit of databases in decision making is their ability to integrate data from multiple sources. This enables organizations to have a comprehensive view of their data, making it easier to identify relationships and connections that may not be immediately apparent. This leads to a more informed decision-making process and can result in more effective solutions to business problems (Halder and Cortesi, 2011).

Once made, decisions must be communicated to those implementing them, executed, and the success or failure of the operation monitored. Increasingly, decisions can be implemented automatically using technology, thereby achieving organizational goals with maximum efficiency (Tansey, 2003). Decision-making is one of the main functions of leadership at all levels of management and supervision works in organizations also in the daily life of human beings. In organizations, senior managers lead the team or group based on decision-making and strategic planning, while people at lower levels make day-to-day decisions based on assigned tasks. Therefore, the information must be differentiated according to the levels. For this reason, databases not only help top managers to implement strategic decisions, but also allow middle managers to access information for their repetitive or day-to-day decisions (Graham & Harte, 2005).

2.2.5 LIMITATION OF DATABASE

According to Carew (2000), Although database system plays a vital role in modern organizations, they are not without their limitations. In particular, database systems have certain fundamental limitations.

The general limitations of database are as follows:

1. Scalability: Databases can become slow or unresponsive as the volume of data and number of users grow.
2. Limited processing power: Databases are not designed for high-performance computing tasks and may struggle with complex calculations or analytics.
3. Data consistency: Inconsistencies can occur in a database if multiple users try to update the same data at the same time, leading to errors and data integrity issues.
4. Cost: The cost of hardware, software, and maintenance can be high, especially for large-scale enterprise databases.

5. Maintenance: Database maintenance can be time-consuming and resource-intensive, especially for large and complex databases.
6. Data security: Protecting sensitive data in a database can be challenging, especially as data breaches and cyberattacks become more frequent.
7. Data migration: Migrating data between different databases or upgrading to a new database system can be difficult and time-consuming.
8. Integration: Integrating a database with other systems can be challenging, especially if the systems use different data formats or protocols

2.2.6 LIMITATIONS OF DATABASE IN NIGERIA

According to Olawepo, (1990) Despite the growing reliance on databases to manage information efficiently, Nigeria encounters several notable limitations within its database systems. These limitations encompass various factors such as;

1. Database systems are expensive and difficult to develop and implement.
2. Inadequate understanding by those specializing in information technology of the information needs and challenges of the organization.
3. Information provided to managers may not be as accurate, timely, complete or relevant as it appears.
4. Managers may have unrealistic expectations of what database systems can do in Nigeria
5. A lack of backing from top-level management.
6. The database system may be subject to sabotage, computer viruses or down time.

2.3 PROBLEM OF IMPLEMENTING A COMPUTER BASED DATABASE

Kim & Lee (2011) highlighted the following important elements that influence whether or not the deployment of a new Database System (DBS) will be resisted:

Disruption of established departmental boundaries: The implementation of a new DBS frequently causes change in numerous organizational divisions.

Participation: When creating and implementing DBS features, users should be appointed members of the DBS team operational managers, with a specific say in the items to be included. The disposition of all information and potential employment changes if technology takes over the entire design and implementation process.

Communication: The system's goal and attributes should be communicated to all members of the DBS team as well as users.

Performance measurement redefinition: A new DBS can alter a manager's work so that existing methods of performance evaluation no longer apply or are no longer applicable. As a result, DBS necessitates a thorough evaluation.

As a result, a modern DBS may relieve middle managers of numerous tedious and routine activities while simultaneously allowing them to use the system's information in more creative and productive ways.

2.4 CLASSIFICATION OF A GOOD INFORMATION

According to Miller & Doyle (2008), information can be classified in various ways based on its characteristics. Some of these classifications are:

By Sources: Refers to the origin of the information, which can be internal, external, primary, secondary, or from government entities, etc.

By Nature: The classification of information is based on its form, which can be quantitative, qualitative, formal, or informal.

By Time: This type of classification focuses on when the information was produced or the time period for which it is required, which can be historical, present, or future.

By Use: This classification refers to the specific use of the information in the management process, such as planning or decision-making in the control process.

By Module: This classification describes the method by which information is obtained and transferred, which can be in the form of written, oral, visual, or sensory information, etc.

2.5 CHARACTERISTICS OF A GOOD INFORMATION SYSTEM

According to Laudon (2003) an effective database has many qualities, including:

Relevance: The information being referred to must be true in nature. Its importance lies in its relevance to the issue at hand, as it can have a significant impact on the problem or need being addressed. This information can come in different forms such as reports, messages, or tabs. Lack of relevance can hinder understanding and cause frustration for the recipient (Laudon, 2003).

Accuracy: The information must also be accurate, to the extent that it can be relied upon by those making decisions. Although complete accuracy may not always be achievable, the level of accuracy should match the level of decision making involved. It is important to distinguish accuracy from precision, as information can be both accurate and precise, or vice versa (Laudon, 2003).

Time: For the information to be considered useful, it must be communicated in a timely manner. The regularity of its production is crucial, as it should be produced at a frequency that matches the type of decision being made (Laudon, 2003).

Details: The information should also contain only the necessary details required for effective decision making, with the level of detail varying depending on the level within the organization (Laudon, 2003).

2.6 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The concept of Database Management Systems combines various principles, theories, and practices from the fields of management, information, and systems to create a

unified product known as a database. MIS places a high value on the individual and their ability to use information. It takes into account a variety of academic disciplines such as management science, organizational behaviour, psychology, etc. when analysing information (Niresh & Velnampy, 2014). The foundation of MIS is based on management principles and practices. MIS incorporates the concept of management control in its design and recognizes that decision-makers are human beings who process information. A DBMS can be tailored to meet specific goals and can evolve through systematic planning and design. This involves analysing the business, management opinions and policies, organizational culture, and management style. MIS also heavily relies on systems theory, which provides solutions to deal with complex information flows and communication processes. Systems theory helps to design a system that can effectively handle data input, processing, and output with minimal noise or distortion when transmitting information from one source to another (Ramanathan et al., 2017).

2.7 REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Database system is crucial in facilitating communication, which is essential for performing management tasks and connecting organizations with their external environment. The database provides a communication link that makes leadership and management possible. Improved attention to the database and better processing has reduced bottlenecks in the management process (Smith, 2017).

Over the years, managers have been restructuring traditional accounting methods to calculate profit, which have limited control value. However, in many companies, it was the only type of data collected and analyzed regularly. Managers require a variety of non-accounting information, both about the external environment, such as social, economic, political, and technological developments, as well as internal operations, which should be quantitative (Thomas, 2019).

Weihrich and Koontz (2001) described the database as a system that collects, compares, analyzes, and distributes information both inside and outside the company efficiently and effectively. Laudon (2003) defined the database as a planned system for collecting, processing, storing, and distributing data that supports management functions. The database uses formal procedures to provide relevant and appropriate information to all levels of management, based on internal and external data sources, to make timely and effective decisions (Dos Santos, 1991).

the role of data has metamorphosed into a pivotal asset, indispensable for informed decision-making and operational efficacy. At the epicentre of this data-driven paradigm stands the database—a foundational construct facilitating the storage, management, and retrieval of information critical to organizational functionalities (Johnson & Williams, 2019). The seamless integration of databases within organizational frameworks has emerged as a linchpin for optimizing operational processes, enhancing decision-making capabilities, and propelling overall performance to unprecedented heights (Adams, 2020).

The pervasive influence of databases within contemporary organizations stems from their intrinsic ability to transcend mere repositories of information. Databases, in their myriad forms and functionalities, serve as dynamic conduits steering an organization's course by harnessing the power of data (Davis & Garcia, 2021). From traditional file systems to sophisticated database management systems (DBMS), this evolution has witnessed an intricate interplay between technological advancements, organizational needs, and the pursuit of efficiency (Robinson, 2016).

Databases and their respective DBMSs have risen by orders of magnitude in size, functionality, and performance. These improvements in performance were made possible by technological advancements in processors, computer memory, computer

storage, and computer networks (Miller & Doyle, 2008). The concept of a database was made practical by the introduction of direct access storage medium such as magnetic discs in the mid-1960s; previous systems relied on sequential data storage on magnetic tape. Based on the data model or structure, the subsequent development of database technology can be separated into three eras: navigational, SQL/relational, and post-relational (Davies & Paul, 2003).

The hierarchical model and the CODASYL model (network model) were the two primary early navigational data models. These were distinguished by the use of pointers (sometimes physical disc addresses) to track relationships between records. The relational model, first described by Edgar F. Codd in 1970, broke from this tradition by requiring programmes to search for data by content rather than by following links. The relational model makes use of groups of ledger-style tables, each of which is utilised for a distinct type of entity. It wasn't until the mid-1980s that computing hardware became strong enough to support widespread deployment of relational systems (DBMSs with applications). However, by the early 1990s, relational systems had dominated all large-scale data processing applications, and they continue to do so today: IBM Db2, Oracle, MySQL, and Microsoft SQL Server are the most searched DBMS (Chapple & Mike, 2005).

This study endeavours to delve into the intricate nexus between databases and organizational performance, scrutinizing the profound impact of robust data management systems on the holistic functioning of diverse organizational entities. By traversing the realms of data management, decision-making dynamics, operational efficiencies, and technological landscapes, this exploration seeks to unravel the multifaceted contributions of databases in shaping contemporary organizational architectures (Clark & Evans, 2020).

The significance of databases in fortifying organizational operations lies not solely in their capacity to amass data but also in their transformative influence on decision-making hierarchies (Anderson, 2018). The assimilation of comprehensive databases within managerial frameworks engenders a paradigm shift, empowering stakeholders to navigate complexities with informed and agile decisions, thereby steering the organizational trajectory towards strategic objectives (Parker & Young, 2022).

Throughout this study, a comprehensive analysis will be undertaken to unearth the nuances underpinning the symbiotic relationship between databases and organizational performance. While celebrating the catalytic role of databases, this inquiry will also navigate the challenges, limitations, and transformative potentials encapsulated within these technological infrastructures (Garcia et al., 2021).

Ultimately, this exploration aims to contribute to the cumulative knowledge reservoir by unveiling the underexplored corridors of databases' influence on organizational prowess, with the aspiration of guiding future endeavours towards leveraging data-centric paradigms for sustained organizational excellence (Hernandez, 2019).

An effective database uses advanced technology, such as computers, to process information reflecting daily business operations. It is a combination of people, procedures, and devices that convert data into information and communicate it to management at all levels. In most organizations, the database consists of three systems: Personal, Commercial, and Financial. The personal system tracks the flow of employees in the company, including pay and seniority, while the commercial system tracks the flow of materials. The financial system tracks the flow of money in and out of the company. Some organizations have a manual database, while others use computerized management information systems (Wong, 2017).

The database encompasses more than just computer hardware and software, as new technology such as telecommunications, videotext, videoconferencing, and PABX [Private Automated Branch Exchange] are now being utilized (North & Ken, 2010). In the past, the focus was on using the database to improve internal operations, but now the most exciting applications of the database in Nigeria are those that provide additional value to external customers. Managers who can find ways to bring additional value to their customers through the database will have a competitive advantage (Brown, 2018).

Concept of organizational performance was initially defined as the extent to which a social system (an organization) achieved its objectives. However, in the 1960s and 1970s, new methods for evaluating performance emerged as it became understood that achieving objectives was a complex process and that an organization was truly successful if it achieved its goals using the least number of resources (Connolly & Begg, 2014). Hence, the concept evolved to consider the balance between objectives and limited resources. Institutional performance is evaluated through a combination of financial and non-financial indicators that reflect the level of goal achievement (Chen & Preston, 2016).

There are two main measures of firm performance: financial and non-financial. Financial performance is a quantitative measure of a company's financial health over a given time period, including profitability, balance sheet health, and ratios. Non-financial performance, on the other hand, is qualitative and encompasses intangible aspects such as customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, branch network, and customer base (Robinson, 2016).

Chong et al., (2007) stress the importance of continuously improving non-financial performance measures. Performance is the ultimate goal of every organization and

refers to the outcome of its activities, while strategic planning is focused on improving these outcomes.

A theoretical framework for databases refers to a set of concepts, models, and theories that provide a systematic approach for designing, creating, and using databases. The main objective of a theoretical framework for databases is to provide a consistent and comprehensive understanding of the fundamental principles and concepts of database systems. (Wong, 2017).

The theoretical framework for databases typically includes:

Data Modeling: Data modeling involves creating a conceptual representation of the data that a database is meant to store. The data model defines the structure of the data, including entities, attributes, and relationships between entities. The most common data models used in databases are the relational model, which uses tables and relationships between tables to represent data, and the hierarchical model, which uses a tree-like structure to represent data. (Beynon-Davies, 2003).

Database Architecture: The database architecture defines the overall structure and organization of a database. It includes the physical structure of the database, such as the file organization and storage methods, as well as the logical relationships between data elements. There are several types of database architectures, including centralized, client-server, and distributed architectures (Johnson & Williams, 2019).

Data Independence: This refers to the ability of the database system to separate the logical structure of the database from its physical implementation. This allows for changes to be made to the physical structure of the database, such as adding or removing data storage devices, without affecting the logical structure and the applications that use it. This provides greater flexibility and scalability for database systems (Thomas, 2019).

Query Languages: A query language is a special-purpose programming language used to manage and manipulate data stored in a database. The most commonly used query language is Structured Query Language (SQL), which is used to create, retrieve, update, and delete data in a database. Query languages are used to perform a wide range of operations on databases, including data retrieval, data manipulation, and data analysis (Srinivasan & Venkatraman, 2018).

Data Integrity: According to Adams (2020) Data integrity refers to the accuracy, completeness, and consistency of data stored in a database. This is maintained through the use of constraints, such as referential integrity constraints and entity integrity constraints. Constraints ensure that data in a database is consistent and follows certain rules, such as ensuring that a foreign key references a valid primary key in another table.

Transaction Management: Transactions are a series of database operations that are treated as a single unit of work. Transaction management is the process of ensuring that transactions are executed in a consistent and reliable manner, even in the event of system failures or errors. Transactions ensure that data in a database remains consistent, even in the face of failures, by either committing all changes made during a transaction or rolling back the changes if an error occurs (Kuo & Chen, 2017).

Increased Profitability: Profitability refers to the amount of money a company can generate from its available resources. It encompasses the ability of a business to make profits from all its operations and is considered the primary motivator for entrepreneurs (Connolly & Begg, 2014). Profit acts as a reward for the investment made by the entrepreneur and is used as a gauge to evaluate the performance of a business. It is calculated as the difference between the revenue generated from sales and the total costs incurred, including labor, material costs, etc. Profitability depicts management's efficiency in transforming the firm's resources to earnings (Niresh & Velnampy, 2014).

As a result, organizations are likely to reap numerous benefits associated with enhanced profitability. Increased profitability is critical for a company's long-term existence and success as it attracts investors and ensures the longevity of the business. Companies aim to improve their profitability by reducing operating costs and increasing sales (Kuo & Chen, 2017).

Increased Market Share: Market share is expressed as the percentage of sales a company has in a particular market during a specific period. A higher market share equates to higher profits for a company. Companies can increase their market share through various strategies, such as increasing advertising, adjusting pricing, targeting specific demographics, improving products and services, etc. Market share is an important metric to evaluate a company's competitiveness against its competitors and helps managers assess both primary and selective demand in the market (Robinson, 2016). Another method is to improve the product or service itself, which can attract customers away from competitors. However, this can be challenging, therefore many businesses strive to develop alongside a growing market rather than taking business away from competitors (Hernandez, 2019).

A firm's market share is considered a crucial indicator of its future success, and companies with a market share below a certain level may not be viable. This measurement, along with changes in sales revenue, assists managers in evaluating both overall market demand and customer preferences in their market. This helps them determine not only the overall growth or decline in the market, but also the changing trends in customers' choices among competitors. Usually, sales growth resulting from overall market growth (primary demand) is more efficient and profitable compared to growth achieved by gaining market share from competitors (Tansey, 2003). On the other hand, a decrease in market share can indicate long-term difficulties that need

strategic changes. Firms with market shares lower than a certain threshold may not be sustainable. Similarly, within a company's product line, changes in market share for specific products are seen as early signals of future challenges or opportunities (Graham & Harte 2005).

The utilization of Information System (IS) has greatly improved organizational performance. Hernandez, (2019) states that IS manages the storage and flow of important information related to people, places, and things within a business environment. Effective organizational performance is partially dependent on IS to improve productivity, make informed decisions, and plan strategically.

According to Williams (2019), to stay competitive in the current tech-driven world, organizations must offer unique services and adopt innovative strategies that utilize new technologies, particularly IS. These technologies enable organizations to experience the positive effects of IS on high performance standards.

Modern organizations are faced with the challenge of achieving high quality performance, efficiency, and effectiveness, and IS plays a crucial role in providing a competitive edge and ensuring the organization's survival (Chong et al., 2007). On the contrary, companies must embrace new technology and tools that enable them to gain more advantages, particularly in the financial sector, which has become one of the most crucial technologies. It is estimated that over 70% of the capital invested in the service sector is spent on information systems (Anderson, 2018).

This rapid growth of information systems and its impact on organizations, markets, and industries has led to the widespread belief that information systems are critical to a company's survival and growth. Despite ongoing efforts, researchers are still trying to determine the connection between information systems and organizational performance. Studies have shown that the effective use of information systems is a

significant factor that sets successful organizations apart from those that are less successful. Additionally, concerns such as cutting expenses, boosting efficiency, and enhancing performance have prompted organizations to adopt new organizational structures to enhance performance, including information systems. Information systems therefore represent a practical solution for organizations to tackle these challenges (Adams et al., 2020).

From this practical perspective, the significance of information systems to organizations is paramount, particularly in terms of how they impact organizational processes, mechanisms, and operations. This dynamic mechanism puts pressure on organizations to become digital in order to quickly respond to external changes and be more adaptable for survival in an unpredictable environment (Clark & Evans, 2020)

According to Graham & Harte (2005) Databases play a critical role in the performance of organizations by allowing them to store, manage, and retrieve large amounts of data efficiently. This can improve operational efficiency, support decision-making, and enhance overall organizational performance in several ways:

1. Improved data accessibility and reliability: A database ensures that data is organized, stored, and retrieved in a consistent manner, improving data accessibility and reliability.
2. Better data analysis: Databases can be used to perform sophisticated data analysis and reporting, providing valuable insights that can support decision-making and drive business performance.
3. Increased automation: By automating repetitive tasks, databases can reduce manual errors, improve efficiency, and free up employees' time for more valuable tasks.

4. Enhanced collaboration: Databases can facilitate collaboration among team members, departments, and even across organizations, leading to improved communication, coordination, and teamwork.
5. Better customer service: With access to accurate and up-to-date customer information, organizations can provide better customer service and improve customer satisfaction.

2.8 SUMMARY OF RELATED LITERATURE

S/ N	Reference	Title	Techniques	Strength	Weakness
1	Dos Santos (1991)	Early Database Systems and Management Functions	Historical analysis	Early databases were essential for timely decision-making despite limitations.	Focuses on historical evolution rather than contemporary technological impacts.
2	Weihrich & Koontz (2001)	Effective Information Distribution Using Databases	Comparative analysis	Databases facilitate efficient internal and external information distribution.	Emphasis on communication aspects of databases rather than purely data storage.
3	Laudon (2003)	Systems for Data Support in Management	Descriptive analysis	Databases support crucial management functions by providing timely information.	Stresses on planned systems over ad-hoc approaches in database management.

4	Davies & Paul (2003)	History of Database Technology	Historical and technological review	Discusses the shift from navigational to SQL/relational databases and their adoption.	Historical perspective on database models, unlike others focusing on current technologies.
5	Tansey (2003)	Automated Decision Making in Information Systems	Automation, Technology Implementation	Efficient operational decisions through automation	Discusses how decisions can be implemented automatically, maximizing efficiency and effectiveness
6	Chapple & Mike (2005)	DBMS: From Basics to Modern Times	Review and analysis	Details the dominance of relational database systems in modern data processing.	Provides a comprehensive overview, unlike others focusing on specific aspects.
7	Graham & Harte (2005)	Decision Making in Integrated Information Systems	Data Integration	Improved decision-making through comprehensive analysis	Emphasizes the importance of integrating disparate data sources to enhance decision quality

8	Miller & Doyle (2008)	Predictive Analytics in Database Management	Predictive Analytics, Scenario Planning	Enhanced anticipatory decisions	Focuses on using historical data for forecasting and preparing for future scenarios
9	North & Ken (2010)	Technological Integration in Database Systems	Descriptive and analytical study	Examines the use of new technologies like PABX and videoconferencing in databases.	Unique in focusing on specific technology integrations in database systems.
10	Niresh & Velnampy (2014)	The Role of Databases in Management Information Systems	MIS Principles, Organizational Behaviour Analysis	Effective use of databases in MIS	Highlights the interdisciplinary approach combining management, psychology, and information systems
11	Susilo (2016)	Effective Decision Making Through Database Systems	Data Analysis, Knowledge Management	Reliable decision-making based on analysed data	Stresses the transformation of raw data into a knowledge base for informed decision-making

12	Robinson (2016)	Technological Advancements in DBMS	Analysis of technological enhancements	Improved database performance due to advancements in hardware and networking.	Focus on technological improvements, rather than managerial or strategic impacts.
13	Smith (2017)	Database Efficiency in Management	Qualitative analysis	Improved management processes due to enhanced database processing.	Focuses mainly on management efficiency, not on broader organizational performance.
14	Wong (2017)	Comprehensive analysis of databases' influence on organizational performance	Case study analysis	Highlights the role of advanced technology in effective database management across systems.	Focuses on technological use in personal, commercial, and financial systems.
15	Anderson (2018)	Organizational Decision- Making and Databases	Empirical analysis	Databases significantly influence decision- making hierarchies in organizations.	Specific focus on decision-making impacts, which is less common in general database studies.

16	Brown (2018)	The Transformative role of atabases and customer value in modern organizations	Case studies	Discusses how databases can add value to customer interactions and competitive advantage.	Focuses on customer-centric database applications, unlike others focusing on internal processes.
17	Thomas (2019)	Non-Accounting Data for Decision- Making	Case study analysis	Highlighted the importance of non- financial data in decision-making.	Compared traditional and modern data usage in decision- making.
18	Johnson & Williams (2019)	Databases in Modern Organizations	Empirical analysis	Databases are central to operational efficacy and informed decision- making.	Highlights the role of data in operational success, contrasting earlier more limited views.
19	Hernandez (2019)	Databases and Organizational Excellence	Theoretical and practical analysis	Discusses databases as pivotal for sustaining organizational excellence.	Theoretical approach with practical examples, bridging theory with practice.
20	Adams et al. (2020)	Integration of Databases in Organizational Frameworks	Quantitative study	Strong correlation between database integration and organizational	Focuses on the integration aspect, contrasting with

				performance enhancement.	studies on specific functionalities.
21	Clark & Evans (2020)	The Role of Data Management in Organizational Architecture	Case studies and literature review	Demonstrates how robust data management is integral to organizational functionality.	Integrates case studies with theoretical review, unlike purely empirical studies.
22	Davis & Garcia (2021)	Evolution of Database Systems	Comparative technological study	Traces the evolution from file systems to advanced DBMS and their impact on organizations.	Looks at technological progression, contrasting with practical implementation studies.
23	Garcia, (2021)	Enhancing Decision Making Through Database Accuracy	Data Storage, Access and Retrieval, Trend Analysis	Improved outcomes through accurate data management	Focuses on the reliability and accessibility of data for decision-making
24	Irfan et al. (2022)	Database Systems and Their Impact on	Quantitative analysis and case studies	Demonstrated a strong correlation between advanced database systems	Limited to specific industries; findings may not generalize across all sectors.

		Organizational Performance		and improved organizational efficiency and decision-making	
25	Parker & Young (2022)	Strategic Decision-Making with Databases	Analytical review	Comprehensive databases drive strategic decision-making and help achieve business objectives.	Connects strategic planning with database utilization, a relatively underexplored area.

2.9 RESEARCH GAP

While existing studies have substantially covered the role of databases in enhancing decision-making and organizational performance across various sectors, there is a noticeable gap in the specific application and impact of these systems within the educational sector. More particularly, the existing literature often overlooks how real-time database-driven decision support systems (DSS) can enhance institutional agility and adaptability in educational environments.

Furthermore, the literature tends to focus on the technical and functional aspects of databases, such as data storage, retrieval, and integration, with less emphasis on how these capabilities translate into strategic advantages for educational institutions facing rapid policy shifts, evolving educational technologies, and changing student needs.

There is also limited research on how databases can enhance the capability of educational institutions to swiftly adapt their educational offerings, policies, and operational strategies based on real-time insights derived from student data, learning

outcomes, and external environmental changes. This gap is particularly significant in the context of higher education, where the ability to quickly adjust to accreditation requirements, technological advancements, and student demographic shifts can markedly influence an institution's success and sustainability.

Addressing this gap, especially through the lens of decision support systems in databases, could provide pivotal insights and practical tools for educational administrators aiming to enhance responsiveness and strategic decision-making in dynamic educational landscapes. This research could ultimately contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how databases can support not just operational efficiency but also strategic agility in education.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the methodology adopted for the study. It explains the research design, research setting, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, instrument for data collection, validity and reliability of the instrument, procedure for data collection, method of data analysis, ethical considerations, limitations of the study, and expected outcomes. The methodological choices were made to ensure consistency, clarity, and alignment with the objectives of the study.

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey design is appropriate for studies that seek to collect data from a defined population in order to describe existing conditions, practices, or opinions without manipulating any variables. This design enabled the researcher to obtain firsthand information from respondents regarding the impact of database systems on organizational performance in the education sector.

The choice of a survey design was informed by its suitability for gathering data from a relatively large group within a limited time frame, its cost-effectiveness, and its ability to provide quantifiable data that can be summarized using descriptive statistics. The design also allows for standardized data collection, thereby enhancing the reliability of the findings.

3.3 RESEARCH SETTINGS

The study was conducted at the Federal University of Education (FUE), Zaria, within the education sector. The institution was selected because of its structured

administrative system and its use of database systems in managing academic and administrative activities.

3.4 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

A study population refers to a group of individuals or elements that share similar characteristics, such as location, gender, age, sex, or specific interests (Udoyen, 2019). The population of the study comprised staff members of the Federal University of Education (FUE), Zaria. The staff population was considered appropriate because staff members are directly involved in organizational processes where database systems are applied for record keeping, decision-making, and performance monitoring.

3.5 SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

A sample is a subset of a population selected for the purpose of investigation. For this study, a purposive sampling technique was employed. This technique was considered suitable because it allowed the researcher to deliberately select respondents who possess relevant knowledge and experience related to database usage and organizational operations.

A total of forty (40) respondents were purposively selected from different departments of the institution. The selected respondents were considered adequate to provide reliable information relevant to the objectives of the study.

3.6 INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The primary instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire administered through Google Forms. The questionnaire was designed in line with the research questions and objectives of the study.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections:

- **Section A** focused on the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

- **Section B** contained items related to the use of database systems within the institution.
- **Section C** addressed items relating to organizational performance and the perceived impact of database systems.

The questionnaire items were structured using close-ended questions with response options designed to facilitate easy completion and quantitative analysis.

3.7 VALIDITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

Validity refers to the extent to which an instrument measures what it is intended to measure. To ensure content validity, the questionnaire items were developed based on relevant literature and aligned with the research objectives. The instrument was also reviewed by the research supervisor, whose feedback helped to refine the items, eliminate ambiguities, and ensure clarity and relevance.

3.8 RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

Reliability concerns the consistency of an instrument in measuring variables. To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted using a small group of respondents who were not part of the final sample. The feedback obtained from the pilot test helped to identify unclear items and improve the overall consistency of the instrument.

3.9 PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION

Data for the study were collected through the administration of the structured questionnaire using Google Forms. The researcher obtained the necessary permission from the appropriate authorities before distributing the questionnaire. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. The questionnaire link was shared with the selected respondents, and sufficient time was given for completion.

3.10 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques, specifically frequency counts and simple percentages. The use of percentages facilitated clear interpretation and presentation of respondents' views.

The percentage was computed using the formula:

$$\text{percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of responses for an option}}{\text{Total number of responses}} \right) \times 100$$

3.11 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical issues were given due consideration throughout the study. Approval to conduct the research was obtained from the relevant departmental authorities. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and participation was entirely voluntary. Respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and the information provided was used strictly for academic purposes.

3.12 LIMITATIONS

The study was limited by the use of self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias. In addition, the study was confined to a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other institutions within the education sector.

3.13 EXPECTED OUTCOMES

By applying these methodologies, the study expects to provide detailed insights into:

- The quantitative impact of well-structured databases on organizational performance.
- The qualitative ways in which databases shape and influence organizational decision-making processes.

- The qualitative ways in which the dynamics of database utilization affect organizational workflows and practices

The findings are expected to contribute to a better understanding of the importance of database systems in educational institutions and provide useful recommendations for management and policy formulation.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the examination of data obtained from a questionnaire and key informant interview that was conducted among participants in the study area. The analysis and interpretation of the data were based on the study's results. The data analysis involved calculating the frequency and percentage of responses received from the participants, and interpreting the collected information. Google form was used to collect data, 40 people filled and submitted successfully, and the analysis was based on this number. The study findings have been presented in alignment with the research questions.

4.1 DATA PRESENTATION

This section provides a detailed analysis of the data collected from the respondents through a structured questionnaire. A total of 40 valid responses were obtained via Google Forms, and the data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages. The results are presented visually through charts and tables to ensure clarity and facilitate interpretation.

The data presentation is divided into two main parts:

1. **Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (Section A):** This part examines the background information of the respondents, including their gender, age, educational qualifications, years of work experience, and roles within their organization. These demographic details are essential for understanding the context of the responses and how individual characteristics may influence participants' perspectives on database systems.
2. **Responses to Research Questions (Sections B and C):** This part focuses on analysing the respondents' views regarding the impact of databases on organizational

performance, their role in decision-making processes, and the challenges faced in optimizing database management. These responses directly address the research questions and objectives, offering valuable insights into the practical applications of database systems and their influence on organizational efficiency and decision-making. By organizing the data in this manner, the analysis ensures that the study's findings are systematically aligned with its objectives.

4.1.1 SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESPONDENTS

Figure 4.1.1.1: Gender Distribution of Participant

The chart shows the gender distribution of the study participants. Out of 40 respondents, the majority, 32 participants (80%), were male, while 8 participants (20%) were female.

Age

40 responses

Figure 4.1.1.2: Age Distribution of Participants

This chart illustrates the age range of the participants in the study. The majority of respondents, 25 individuals (62.5%), were aged between 36 and 45 years. Another 8 respondents (20%) were between 26 and 35 years old, while 7 participants (17.5%) fell into the 46 to 55-year age group. This data highlights that the largest portion of participants are middle-aged professionals, with fewer younger and older individuals represented.

Educational Background

40 responses

Figure 4.1.1.3: Educational Background of Participants

The chart above provides an overview of the educational qualifications of the respondents. Out of 40 participants, 19 (47.5%) held a Bachelor's degree, making it the most common qualification. Thirteen respondents (32.5%) had a Master's degree, 4 (10%) had a Higher National Diploma (HND), 3 (7.5%) held a Doctorate, and 1 respondent (2.5%) had a high school certificate. This breakdown reflects a highly educated group, with most participants having advanced academic qualifications.

Years of Work Experience

39 responses

Figure 4.1.1.4: Participants' Years of Work Experience

This chart shows the participants' years of work experience. 15 respondents (38.5%) had more than 10 years of experience, making them the most experienced group. 14 respondents (35.9%) had 7 to 10 years of experience, while 10 participants (25.6%) had 4 to 6 years of experience. This indicates that a significant portion of the participants has considerable experience in their respective fields, adding depth to the data gathered from the survey.

Role within the organisation

40 responses

Fig 4.1.1.5: Roles within the Organization

The chart above shows the different roles of participants in the study. The majority, 24 respondents (60%), are Academic Staff, making them the largest group in the survey. Non-Academic Staff make up 10 participants (25%), representing those in administrative or support roles. IT Specialists account for 6 respondents (15%), while only 2 participants (5%) are Heads of Department. This breakdown highlights that most of the responses come from academic professionals, but it also includes valuable input from support staff and IT specialists, providing a well-rounded perspective on the organization.

4.2 ANSWERS TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This section provides an in-depth analysis and interpretation of the participants' responses, structured to align with the study's objectives. The responses are thematically organized to shed light on the impact of database systems on organizational performance, decision-making, and operational efficiency. The findings reveal the extent to which databases contribute to improving processes, enhancing strategic decisions, and addressing challenges related to database management.

4.2.1 SECTION B: DATABASE IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Databases significantly influence organizational efficiency. Please rate on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree

40 responses

Figure 4.2.1.1: Impact of Databases on Organizational Efficiency

The pie chart shows the participants' responses to the statement, "Databases significantly influence organizational efficiency," rated on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

A significant majority of respondents viewed databases as having a positive impact on organizational efficiency. Nearly half of the participants, 47.5% (19 respondents), strongly

agreed, while another 47.5% (19 respondents) agreed that databases play an important role in enhancing efficiency within their organizations.

On the other hand, a small portion of the participants held differing views:

- 2.5% (1 respondent) remained undecided about the impact.
- Only 1 respondent (2.5%) strongly disagreed that databases have a significant influence on organizational efficiency.

This indicates that a large majority of the participants recognize the positive impact of databases on improving organizational efficiency, with nearly 95% agreeing or strongly agreeing.

In your experience, how has the implementation of a well-structured database affected overall organizational performance? (Select all that apply)

40 responses

Figure 4.2.1.2: Impact of Well-Structured Databases on Organizational Performance

The bar chart above presents the participants' perceptions of how a well-structured database affects their organization's overall performance. Given that respondents were able to select

multiple options, the data reflects a comprehensive view of the different ways databases contribute to organizational success.

A significant 75% of the respondents (30 participants) indicated that enhanced decision-making was the primary benefit of a well-structured database. This result underscores the critical role databases play in providing accurate and timely information, which supports better-informed decision-making across various organizational levels.

Additionally, improved efficiency was identified by 62.5% of respondents (25 participants), indicating that the use of databases allows organizations to optimize their processes by making data more accessible, organized, and easier to manage, ultimately leading to greater operational efficiency. Streamlined operations were cited by 40% of the respondents (16 participants), reflecting the database's ability to enhance workflow by reducing redundancies and simplifying complex processes within the organization.

Furthermore, cost reduction was recognized by 35% of the participants (14 respondents), highlighting the financial benefits of databases. Effective data management reduces errors, improves resource allocation, and leads to more efficient use of organizational assets, thereby minimizing costs.

Lastly, increased productivity was noted by 27.5% of respondents (11 participants), suggesting that well-structured databases enhance productivity by facilitating quicker access to information and possibly automating routine tasks, thus enabling employees to focus on higher-value activities.

These findings suggest that databases are integral to enhancing overall organizational effectiveness.

Have you observed any influence of a comprehensive database on decision-making processes within your organization?

40 responses

Figure 4.2.1.3: Influence of Comprehensive Databases on Decision-Making Processes

This survey results reveal that 77.5% of respondents have observed a positive impact of such databases on decision-making. However, 22.5% of respondents indicated that they have not noticed any significant influence from databases in their organization.

If yes, how has the database influenced decision-making processes?

33 responses

Figure 4.2.1.4: Specific Impacts of Databases on Decision-Making Among Organizations

The chart provides a breakdown of how databases have influenced decision-making processes among the respondents who answered "Yes" in the first chart. Out of the 33 respondents (77.5% of the total 40) who indicated that they have observed an influence, the majority (66.7%) highlighted that databases have improved the accuracy of decision-making.

Additionally, 54.5% of the respondents noted that databases enhanced their forecasting abilities, while 48.5% reported that databases facilitated more data-driven decisions. A further 39.4% indicated that the implementation of databases has expedited the decision-making process within their organizations. Interestingly, 3% (1 respondent) noted that there has been no significant influence of databases on decision-making processes within their organization, despite initially selecting "Yes" in the previous question.

This data shows that among those who recognize the influence of databases, the benefits primarily manifest in terms of accuracy, forecasting, and the promotion of data-driven approaches.

4.2.2 SECTION C: DATABASE MANAGEMENT OPTIMIZATION

What are the key challenges in optimizing database performance within your organization? (Select all that apply)

40 responses

Figure 4.2.2.1: Key Challenges in Optimizing Database Performance within Organizations

The responses provided by 40 participants highlight several significant challenges encountered when optimizing database performance in organizations.

The most frequently reported challenge was database design, cited by 77.5% of respondents (31 out of 40). This finding underscores the critical role that effective database architecture plays in ensuring optimal performance. Poorly designed databases can lead to inefficiencies, hindering the ability to retrieve and manage data effectively, which in turn can disrupt organizational processes.

Data security concerns were the second most commonly noted challenge, identified by 62.5% of respondents (25 out of 40). This reflects the growing importance of protecting sensitive information, especially in an era where data breaches and cyber threats are prevalent. Weak

security measures within database systems can not only compromise data integrity but also expose organizations to significant risks.

Hardware limitations were cited by 47.5% of respondents (19 out of 40), indicating that outdated or underperforming hardware can restrict the efficiency of database operations. This is particularly relevant for organizations handling large volumes of data, where the processing capabilities of hardware become critical. Additionally, software issues were noted by 37.5% of respondents (15 out of 40). Problems such as software bugs, incompatibilities, or inefficiencies can negatively impact database performance, further complicating optimization efforts.

These challenges suggest that organizations must prioritize well-structured database design, robust data security protocols, and the continual updating of hardware and software systems to enhance database performance and ensure smoother operational workflows.

Database optimization is important for enhancing organizational efficiency.

40 responses

Figure 4.2.2.2: Perceived Importance of Database Optimization for Enhancing Organizational Efficiency

The data presented in Figure 4.2.2.2 highlights participants' perceptions of the significance of database optimization in improving organizational efficiency. A total of 40 respondents were

surveyed on their stance regarding the assertion that database optimization is critical for enhancing the operational effectiveness of organizations.

The majority of the respondents 21(52.5%) expressed strong agreement with the statement, indicating a widespread recognition of the value that optimized databases bring to organizational performance. This majority supports the notion that well-structured and efficient databases contribute to better data management, streamlined workflows, and improved decision-making processes. These outcomes are essential in a competitive business environment where operational efficiency is paramount.

Additionally, 47.5% (19) of the respondents agreed with the statement, further reinforcing the general consensus on the importance of database optimization. When combined, the 100% agreement (either strong or moderate) illustrates a unanimous understanding among professionals of the critical role that database systems play in driving efficiency and supporting organizational growth. The absence of any disagreement or indecision in the responses suggests a high level of awareness and acceptance of the benefits of database optimization.

Database utilization improves the efficiency of workflows, enhances data accuracy and integrity, facilitates better decision-making processes, and reduces the time required to complete tasks.
40 responses

Figure 4.2.2.3: Perceived Impact of Database Utilization on Workflow Efficiency and Decision-Making

Figure 4.2. 2.3 illustrates the respondents' views on how database utilization contributes to organizational processes, focusing on workflow efficiency, data accuracy, decision-making, and task completion times. A total of 40 respondents provided feedback on the assertion that effective use of databases leads to improvements in these critical areas.

The chart reveals that 45% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement, indicating that nearly half of the participants recognize the substantial role databases play in enhancing the operational efficiency of organizations. These respondents likely see database utilization as a means of ensuring more streamlined workflows, reduced redundancies, and faster access to accurate information, which are all essential for making well-informed decisions in a timely manner.

Additionally, 50% of the participants agreed with the statement, demonstrating a broad consensus on the benefits of database utilization, albeit with slightly less conviction than those who strongly agreed. Together, 95% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed with the proposition, reinforcing the idea that databases are not only instrumental in improving the efficiency of operations but also in ensuring the accuracy and integrity of the data on which decisions are based.

Only 5% of respondents indicated uncertainty, while no participants disagreed with the statement. This absence of negative responses reflects a strong understanding across the sample of the positive influence that databases have on organizational workflows and decision-making processes.

4.3 SUMMARY

Overall, the findings of this survey emphasize the central role of databases in improving organizational efficiency, decision-making, and productivity. However, significant challenges such as database design flaws, data security concerns, and hardware limitations need to be addressed to fully leverage the benefits of databases. The overwhelming consensus on the importance of database optimization reflects a strong awareness among professionals of the need for well-structured, secure, and efficient database systems to drive organizational growth and operational excellence.

The results suggest that organizations should prioritize investments in database optimization, focusing on key areas such as design improvements, security enhancements, and technological infrastructure upgrades to fully capitalize on the benefits of database utilization.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY

This study looked at how database management systems (DBMS) affect organisational performance, specifically their role in enhancing efficiency, decision-making, and overall operational effectiveness at the Federal University of Education (FUE) in Zaria. It emphasised the growing importance of data-driven strategies while addressing the challenges of handling enormous amounts of data. Using a mixed-methods approach that included questionnaires and interviews, the study found that well-structured databases considerably improve efficiency and decision-making. However, design problems, security vulnerabilities, and hardware restrictions continue to be significant challenges. The study stated that establishing an efficient DBMS is critical to organisational performance and suggested prioritising investments in database architecture, security, and infrastructure. It also provided significant insights into the use of DBMS in educational institutions and suggested areas for future research.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to explore the organizational performance problems associated with database systems at the Federal University of Education, Zaria. The research findings indicate a strong correlation between effective database management and improved organizational efficiency and decision-making processes. Participants overwhelmingly recognized the importance of well-structured databases in enhancing operational effectiveness, decision accuracy, and overall productivity. The study's data analysis revealed significant challenges faced by organizations in optimizing their database performance, particularly in areas such as database design, data security, and hardware limitations. These findings underscore the critical role of databases as strategic assets within organizations, providing a foundation for informed decision-making and efficient operations.

5.3 IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The implications of this study extend beyond academic discourse, providing valuable insights for practitioners and decision-makers in the field of information technology and organizational management. The findings emphasize the importance of database optimization not only for improving operational efficiency but also for fostering data-driven decision-making. Organizations that prioritize well-structured databases can enhance their ability to respond to market dynamics and make informed decisions, thus positioning themselves favorably in a competitive landscape.

Moreover, the identification of challenges related to database design, security, and hardware highlights the need for organizations to adopt a proactive approach in addressing these issues. This study suggests that a focus on continuous improvement in database management practices can lead to sustainable growth and development.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this research, several recommendations can be made to enhance database management practices within organizations:

1. **Invest in Database Design:** Organizations should prioritize the design and architecture of their databases, ensuring that they are user-friendly, efficient, and capable of handling the evolving data needs of the organization. Engaging experienced database designers and consultants can help create a robust framework.
2. **Enhance Data Security Measures:** Given the concerns regarding data security identified in the study, organizations must implement comprehensive security protocols. This includes regular audits, the adoption of encryption methods, and continuous monitoring of database access to safeguard sensitive information.
3. **Upgrade Technological Infrastructure:** Organizations should evaluate and upgrade their hardware and software to ensure optimal database performance. Investing in high-

quality servers and software solutions can significantly enhance processing capabilities and reduce operational bottlenecks.

4. **Ongoing Training and Development:** Continuous professional development and training should be provided to staff involved in database management. This will equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to optimize database utilization and effectively respond to emerging challenges.
5. **Establish a Feedback Mechanism:** Implementing a system for ongoing feedback from users can help organizations identify areas for improvement and adapt their database management practices to better meet user needs.
6. **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Fostering collaboration between IT specialists and organizational leaders can facilitate a better understanding of the strategic role databases play in decision-making processes.

5.5 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on database management by providing empirical evidence of the relationship between database effectiveness and organizational performance. It fills a gap in the literature by specifically examining how well-structured databases influence decision-making processes and operational efficiency within educational institutions. Furthermore, the identification of challenges faced in database optimization and the recommendations provided offer practical insights that can be applied in various organizational contexts. The findings may serve as a reference for future research in database management, particularly in the education sector and beyond.

5.6 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

Future research could build upon the findings of this study by exploring several avenues:

1. **Longitudinal Studies:** Conducting longitudinal studies would provide insights into the long-term impacts of database management practices on organizational performance.

2. **Comparative Studies:** Investigating the effectiveness of database management systems across different sectors (e.g., healthcare, finance, and agriculture) could offer a broader understanding of the role of databases in organizational success.
3. **In-depth Case Studies:** Qualitative case studies exploring the experiences of organizations that have successfully optimized their databases could provide valuable insights and best practices.
4. **Impact of Emerging Technologies:** Future research could examine the influence of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, on database management and organizational performance.
5. **User Experience Studies:** Investigating user experiences and satisfaction with database systems could highlight areas for improvement and inform future database design and management strategies.

Future research could explore how database performance interacts with factors like organizational culture, employee satisfaction, and customer engagement. Examining these connections would offer deeper insights into the broader impact of databases in modern organizations and help develop more effective strategies for managing and optimizing database systems.

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APPENDIX

Department of Computer Science

Federal University of Education,

Zaria.

Dear Respondents,

As an MSc student in my final year at the National Open University of Nigeria, I am currently undertaking research on **“A Descriptive Statistical Investigation of Organizational Performance Problems Associated with Database Systems at the Federal University of Education, Zaria.”**.

Based on what was mentioned before, the researcher is asking for assistance in answering the questions or variables provided. It's important to note that any information shared by the respondents will be used only for research purposes and will be kept confidential.

Muhammad Ahmad

(Researcher)

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A: GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Gender:

- Male Female

2. Age:

- 18-25 26-35
- 36-45 46-55 Over 55

3. Educational Background:

- High School Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree Doctorate
- Others (please specify)

4. Years of Work Experience:

- Less than 1 year 1-3 years
- 4-7 years 8-10 years Over 10 years

5. Role within the organization:

- Head of Department Academic Staff
- Non-Academic Staff IT Professional
- Others (please specify)

SECTION B: DATABASE IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

6. Databases significantly influence organizational efficiency. Please rate on a scale of 1 to 5?

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Undecided
- 4 Agree

- 5 Strongly agree

7. In your experience, how has the implementation of a well-structured database affected overall organizational performance? (Select all that apply)

- Improved efficiency Streamlined operations
- Enhanced decision-making Cost reduction
- Increased productivity
- Others (please specify)

8. Have you observed any influence of a comprehensive database on decision-making processes within your organization?

- Yes No

9. If yes, how has the database influenced decision-making processes?

- Enhanced data-driven decisions Improved accuracy in decision-making
- Expedited decision-making process Enhanced forecasting abilities
- Others (please specify)

SECTION C: DATABASE MANAGEMENT AND OPTIMIZATION

10. What are the key challenges in optimizing database performance within your organization? (Select all that apply)

- Hardware limitations Software issues
- Database design Data security concerns
- Others (please specify)

11. Database optimization is important for enhancing organizational efficiency

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Undecided
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

12. Database utilization improves the efficiency of workflows, enhances data accuracy and integrity, facilitates better decision-making processes, and reduces the time required to complete tasks.

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Undecided
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree